

First record of *Clathrus ruber* from Serbia

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Abstract. A consistent number of records for *Clathrus ruber* have been reported for the Adriatic coast while the presence of this basidiomycete in the continental part of the ex-Yugoslav countries is still rare. In Serbia, *C. ruber* had not been recorded until 1983, when it was found during a botanical field trip. This record has not been published until now, although it is the first record of *C. ruber* for Serbia.

Key words: *Clathrus ruber*, macromycetes, Serbia

Clathrus ruber P. Micheli : Pers. is a widespread species, and its area of distribution extends from North Africa to Northern Europe (Dring 1980; Courtecuisse & Duhem 1994). However, the findings of *C. ruber* outside the Mediterranean area are sporadic, and it is considered a rare species in central Europe.

In the area of the former Yugoslavia (SFRY), *C. ruber* was often found in the Adriatic hinterland, where it is known to the local people as “Witch Heart” (Blagaic 1923, 1930). The findings in the coastal part of Montenegro have been frequent (Jaap 1916; Kuthan 1967; Tortic 1988), as well as in Dalmatia (Picbauer 1928; Lohwag 1935; Barcic 1982). It is far less common in the continental part, for which there is a finding for the Ljubljana area (Lindtner 1934). The data pertaining to the record of this species in Yugoslavia (Courtecuisse & Duhem 1994) refer to the report from Montenegro (ex-Federal Republic of Yugoslavia). Vojteh Lindtner, a mycologist who worked at the Natural History Museum in Belgrade from early thirties until mid-sixties of the 20th century, never mentioned *C. ruber* for this area, in spite of the fact that he made a great collection of mac-

romycetes from Serbia, and that the species was found in the neighbouring Bulgaria (Kuthan & Kotlaba 1981, 1989; Gyosheva *et al.* 2000).

C. ruber was first found in Serbia during a botanical field trip undertaken by Dr. Manfred Fischer and one of the authors (B. Tatic) in October 1983. The collectors have not published the finding of *C. ruber* to this day. Furthermore, the collected specimen was not preserved for herbarium. Fischer and Tatic found the named *C. ruber* specimen next to the Gornji Milanovac – Cacak road, close to the village of Brdjani, near a big curve on the right-hand side of the road in the Gornji Milanovac – Cacak direction. There was only one, completely developed specimen of the fungus. In that site, the soil has been formed on serpentine substrate, with herbaceous vegetation in the surroundings. In the vicinity of the site where *C. ruber* was found, the following plant species characteristic of serpentine were also found: *Notholaena marantae* (L.) Desv., *Potentilla cinerea* Chaix ex Vill., *Medicago prostrata* Jacq., *Halacsya sendtneri* (Boiss.) Dörfler, *Chrysopogon gryllus* (L.) Trin., and *Bromus riparius* Rehmman.

It is interesting to note that the habitat where this specimen of *Clathrus ruber* was found is ultra alkaline serpentine substratum. This is the only specimen found so far in this habitat type in ex-Yugoslav regions.

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Fig. 1. *Clathrus ruber* P. Micheli : Pers., the first specimen from Serbia. Photo: M. Fischer

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